

Article

Goniochromism of Multicolor and Interference Pigments Under Varying Illumination Conditions

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Abstract

Color results from the interaction of objects with varying wavelengths of light and the human visual system's perception under different illumination conditions. In this study, special emphasis was placed on examining how varying illumination conditions and measurement geometries affect the color appearance and optical properties of printed effect pigments. Two distinct groups of pigments were examined: three interference pigments (M-series) based on calcium–aluminum borosilicate substrates, and three multicolor pigments (C-series) based on silicon dioxide. To ensure comparability of the results, all pigments were printed using screen printing techniques onto black PVC film. Characterization involved using a multi-angle spectrophotometer to measure CIEL*a*b* values, chroma (C*), and hue (h*) under CIE standard illuminants D50, A2, and F2 at a fixed illumination angle of 45° and aspecular angles of −15°, 15°, 25°, 45°, 75°, and 110°. Furthermore, the research methodology included the evaluation of lightness difference (ΔL^*), color differences (ΔE^*), chroma difference (ΔC^*), and hue difference (ΔH^*), with the D50 illuminant chosen as the reference and A2 and F2 as sample illuminants. The flop index (FI), as the indicator of lightness change at different scattering angles, was calculated for all printed pigments under all three standard illuminations. This multidisciplinary approach provided a deeper understanding of the relationship between pigment structure, illumination conditions, and viewing angles in our visual perception of printed pigments, which is of great importance for the development and optimization of goniochromatic materials. The results showed that while A2 and F2 illuminants have a negligible impact on lightness differences across all pigments, they induce noticeable variations in color, chroma, and hue differences, particularly at near-specular angles (−15° and 15°). Conversely, these differences become negligible at far-aspecular angles (75° and 110°). Furthermore, flop index (FI) analysis revealed that despite the larger borosilicate flakes in the M-series, the silicon dioxide-based C-series pigments exhibited the highest overall flop effect, with pigment C1 maintaining consistently high FI values under all illuminants.

Keywords: goniochromism; effect pigments; color variability; illuminants; colorimetric properties; flop index; angle-dependent color

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1. Introduction

Color and light are inextricably linked because color is not an inherent property of objects alone, but the result of how those objects interact with different wavelengths of visible light and how the reflected or transmitted light is perceived by the human visual

system under varying illumination conditions. Our visual experience of the environment can be drastically altered by variables including intensity, position, angle of incidence, and even the energy distribution of lighting [1,2].

In nature, coloration arises primarily through two distinct mechanisms: pigmentary color and structural color [3]. Structural colors are prevalent in the natural world and are referred to as visible colors that are produced through the interaction between light and micro- or nanostructures, such as through thin film interference or particle resonance [4,5]. They arise from the interaction between incident light and nanostructures [6]. Structural colors are typically vivid, lustrous, iridescent, or metallic in appearance, arising from physical phenomena such as diffraction, interference, and scattering, usually with minimal energy loss [3,7].

Iridescent and non-iridescent structural colors result from distinct optical interactions between light and structure, such as reflection, refraction, interference, and scattering [4]. Iridescence (Greek word for rainbow—“iridos”), otherwise known as goniochromism, describes the phenomenon of gradual color changes, depending on the angle of view or the angle of illumination [3,8–11]. The observed iridescence can arise from several mechanisms. In some cases, it results from light scattering, which separates white light into its constituent colors, similar to what occurs in a prism. In other instances, it is caused by the interaction of light reflected from different layers within semitransparent bilayer or multilayer structures. Iridescence may also originate from diffraction, an optical phenomenon that occurs when light encounters structural features or irregularities comparable in size to its wavelength, such as small cavities along its path [12].

Special effect pigments are almost exclusively inorganic pigments that provide additional color effects, such as angular color dependence (luster, iridescence, color variability) or texture, when incorporated into coatings, inks, paints, plastics and their subsequent application onto a substrate. The group of special effect pigments includes pearl luster pigments (pearlescent pigments, nacreous pigments) and interference pigments. The visual appearance originates in reflection and deflection of light at thin single and multiple layers [13–15]. Their pronounced reflective properties result from their anisotropic, platelet-like morphology, which is a key difference from conventional pigments that typically have an isotropic, spherical structure. Because of this anisotropic geometry, effect pigments act like microscopic mirrors, reflecting incident light directly back towards its source and thus producing unique visual effects, and are designed to produce visual appearance such as the metallic or pearlescent appearances which have long been associated with goniochromatic effects [14,16]. Interference pigments are defined as effect pigments whose color generating mechanism is based completely or predominantly on the phenomenon of interference. They are based on nontransparent platelets, which lead to different color effects in the application system [15]. Pearl luster pigments give the coating additional color effects, such as an angular color dependence, which is mainly due to the interference of light on thin layers, flakes, or platelets [14,17–19]. On the other hand, they can be produced by coating mica particles with thin layers of metal oxides (TiO_2 , ZrO_2 or SiO_2) to create lustrous, iridescent and other angle-dependent optical effects [7,19].

The visual appearance of prints containing special effect pigments is influenced by several factors, including pigment type, particle size and size distribution, concentration, dispersion state, and the orientation distribution of the particles [20]. The goniochromatic colors produced by special effect pigments are based on the interference effect, in which the incoming light is partly reflected from the particle surface and partly refracted through it [21]. In printing systems that use effect pigments, color shifts are most pronounced when the angle of incidence changes while maintaining a near-aspecular angle (the angle between the viewing and specular directions). At far-aspecular angles, most special-effect

pigments no longer reflect light towards the observer, and the perceived color is instead dominated by conventional diffusely reflecting absorption pigments [22].

Effect pigments are effectively implemented across diverse applications through careful design and optimization, including anti-counterfeiting, coatings, printing, cosmetics, and more, and impart distinctive visual features—such as flop color, pearlescent luster, and angle-dependent interference [14,20].

A review of the scientific literature from the past decade indicates that most previous studies have focused on the visual appearance, optical properties, surface properties, and color fastness of effect pigments applied to various types of substrates [17,20,23–25]. Trujillo-Vazquez et al. compare the behavior of effect pigments in the processes of lithographic and screen printing with standard pigments used in so-called process inks and analyze their optical properties when used on their own or in combination with absorption pigments [23]. Rogelj et al. studied goniospectrometric space curve for coatings with special effect pigments [20]. Rossi et al. investigated durability (gloss, color and roughness) of coatings admixed with pearlescent pigments before, during, and after UVA and UVB exposure [17]. Tomić et al. studied how pearlescent pigment composition and the size of their particles affect lightfastness [24]. Although the goniochromatic behavior of effect pigments is widely recognized, limited attention has been given to understanding how different illumination conditions and measurement geometry influence the color appearance and optical properties of printed effect pigments. The novelty of this study lies in the systematic investigation of the combined influence of illumination and measurement geometry on the color and optical properties of printed interference and multicolor pigments. Unlike previous studies, which predominantly evaluated pigment appearance under a single standard illuminant or fixed viewing conditions, this work examines the pigments under multiple illuminants (D50, A2, and F2) and a wide range of measurement geometries. This approach enables a more comprehensive assessment of illumination-dependent color variability, flop effect, and goniochromatic behavior.

2. Materials and Methods

This study examines the goniochromatic behavior of two groups of effect pigments, which differ in chemical composition, layer structure, density, and particle size distribution, and were printed on black film. Particular attention was given to understanding how these structural and compositional differences influence the optical appearance and color variation of the pigments under changing observation and illumination conditions. Unlike many previous studies that primarily focused on the influence of viewing geometry, the present research examines not only the effect of different viewing angles on the appearance of printed pigments, but also the combined influence of various lighting conditions at multiple observation angles.

2.1. Materials

Black, gloss-coated polyvinyl chloride (PVC) film with a grammage of 150 g/m² was used as a printing material. The physical, optical and surface properties of the PVC film used in this study are presented in Table 1. The grammage, thickness and density were provided by the manufacturer, while gloss and surface roughness were measured in the laboratory as a part of the experimental work.

Table 1. Physical, optical and surface properties of the printing material.

Grammage	Thickness	Density	Gloss 20°/60°/85°	Surface Roughness		
				Ra ¹	Rq ²	Rv ³
150 g/m ²	0.20 mm	750 kg/m ³	53.9/88.4/94.9	0.93 μm ¹	1.92 μm ²	1.90 μm ³

¹ Ra (roughness average) is the arithmetic average of the absolute values of the roughness profile ordinates. ² Rq is the root mean squared of measured microscopic peaks and valleys. ³ Rv is the distance between the deepest valley of the profile and the profile and the mean line within the evaluation length [26].

In this study, six different commercially available effect pigments from Merck (Germany) were used, selected to represent a wide range of colors, composition and particle size relevant to their performance under different illumination conditions. The pigments differed in type (interference and multicolor pigments), chemical composition, density, and particle size distribution. Three interference pigments (M1, M2, M3) were based on calcium–aluminum borosilicate substrates, and three multicolor pigments (C1, C2, C3) were based on silicon dioxide, as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Properties of effect pigments.

Pigment Label	Trade Name	Form	Chemical Composition	Density	Particle Size
M1	Miraval® 5424	Powder	Calcium–Aluminum Borosilicate: 59–77%	2.6–2.8 g/cm ³	20–200 μm
			Silicon Dioxide: 1–8% Titanium Dioxide: 22–32% Tin Oxide: <1%		
M2	Miraval® 5426	Powder	Calcium–Aluminum Borosilicate: 59–75%	2.7–2.9 g/cm ³	20–200 μm
			Silicon Dioxide: 1–5% Titanium Dioxide: 24–35% Tin Oxide: <1%		
M3	Miraval® 5423	Powder	Calcium–Aluminum Borosilicate: 59–77%	2.5–2.9 g/cm ³	20–200 μm
			Silicon Dioxide: 1–8% Titanium Dioxide: 22–32% Tin Oxide: <1%		
C1	Colorstream® T10-01	Powder	Silicon Dioxide: 81–90% Titanium Dioxide: 8–14% Tin Oxide: 2–5%	2.2–2.4 g/cm ³	5–50 μm
C2	Colorstream® T10-02	Powder	Silicon Dioxide: 57–68% Titanium Dioxide: 30–39% Tin Oxide: 2–4%	2.4–2.8 g/cm ³	5–50 μm
C3	Colorstream® T10-03	Powder	Silicon Dioxide: 51–64% Titanium Dioxide: 35–45% Tin Oxide: 1–4%	2.6–2.8 g/cm ³	5–50 μm

2.2. Screen Printing

The PVC film was conditioned to a standard atmosphere of 23 ± 1 °C and 50 ± 2% relative humidity for 24 h before printing. Effect pigments were applied into printing base (PVC transparent base) in 15 wt.% concentration and were printed with screen printing technique (Screen Printer TSH Print Swiss S550) on black PVC film. The mesh density was 120 threads/cm. The color patches of printed pigments are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Color patches of printed effect pigments.

2.3. Measurement Methods

The measurement methods used in this study included surface morphology characterization, colorimetric analysis, and evaluation of the optical properties of the printed pigments under varying illumination and viewing conditions.

The gloss of PVC film was measured at three different angles (20°, 60°, 85°) using QIP GlossMaster multi-angle gloss meter (manufacturer: Ihara, Japan). Measurements conform to the ASTM D523 standard measurement protocol for specular gloss measurements. Gloss is measured in Gloss Units (GU). The surface roughness was measured using a Roughness Tester TR200 (manufacturer: TIME group Inc., China) at automatic measuring range and resolution from 0.01 to 0.04 μm, as presented in Table 1. Before measurement, the printing material was conditioned for 24 h in the standard atmosphere at 23 ± 1 °C and 50 ± 2% relative humidity.

The surface morphology of the pigments was examined using a Scanning Electron Microscope (JSM-6060 LV, JEOL, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV and 500x magnification. A SEM provides high-resolution images by scanning the sample surface with a focused electron beam, enabling observation of particle morphology, size, shape, surface texture, and pigment distribution on the substrate.

CIE colorimetric values (L^* : lightness, a^* : green-red values, b^* : yellow-blue values), chroma (C^*), and hue (h) of the prints were measured using an MA-T12 handheld multi-angle spectrophotometer (manufacturer: X-Rite, Germany) at a fixed illumination angle of 45° and aspecular angles of −15°, 15°, 25°, 45°, 75°, and 110°, as well as under CIE standard illuminants D50, A2, and F2, respectively. The aspecular angle is the viewing angle measured from the specular angle toward the sample normal [27]. Equipped with a polychromatic white LED, the MA-12 provides in-plane reflectance measurements in the range of 400 nm to 700 nm at 10 nm intervals. The multi-spectrophotometer was calibrated according to the manufacturer's instructions to ensure accurate measurements across all angles. To ensure repeatability of the results, each printed sample was measured ten times, and the reported values represent the arithmetic mean of these measurements. The CIE standard illuminant D50, characterized by a correlated color temperature of 5000 K, is commonly used to simulate average daylight conditions, whereas illuminant A2, with a color temperature of 2848 K, corresponds to the spectral output of tungsten-filament lighting, and illuminant F2, with a color temperature of 4200 K, represents typical "cool white" fluorescent lighting [10].

The overall CIE76 color difference (ΔE^*), difference in lightness (ΔL^*), green-red axis (Δa^*), and blue-yellow axis (Δb^*) were calculated according to Equations (1)–(4). The D50 illuminant was chosen as the reference illuminant, and the A2 and F2 illuminants as sample illuminants for the calculation of color difference (ΔE^*), lightness difference (ΔL^*), chroma difference (ΔC^*), as well as hue difference (ΔH^*).

$$\Delta a^* = a_1^* - a_2^* \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta b^* = b_1^* - b_2^* \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta L^* = L_1^* - L_2^* \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2} \quad (4)$$

Values L_1 , a_1 , b_1 refer to the lightness and chromaticity coordinates of color patches under the reference illuminant D50; L_2 , a_2 , b_2 refer to the lightness and chromaticity coordinates of color patches under the sample illuminants A2 and F2.

Chroma (C^*), also known as saturation, describes the brightness (+ indicates brighter) or dullness (- indicates duller) of a color. The chroma difference (ΔC^*) is presented in Equation (5).

$$\Delta C^* = C_1^* - C_2^* \quad (5)$$

Hue (h) is determined by the dominant wavelength of light reflected from an object. The hue difference (ΔH^*) is presented in Equation (6).

$$\Delta H^* = \sqrt{\Delta E^2 - \Delta L^2 - \Delta C^2} \quad (6)$$

A major advantage of the CIELAB system is that color distance can be subdivided into individual components, namely, lightness, chroma, and hue [10,13,28].

Flop index (FI) as a macro-appearance attribute was calculated through the experimental formula of Equation (7), in which L^* is the lightness at 15° , 45° , and 110° near, mid, and far-aspecular angles, respectively.

$$\text{Flop Index (FI)} = \frac{(L_{15^\circ} - L_{110^\circ})^{1.11}}{(L_{45^\circ})^{0.86}} \quad (7)$$

FI = 0 describes a solid color, while FI = 15–17 indicates a high metallic effect. A higher flop index (FI) indicates a more glittering, shinier metallic paint, which provides a better visual impression for the consumer [29,30].

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to evaluate the correlation between illumination conditions and measurement geometries that affect the color appearance and optical properties of printed effect pigments.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Pigment Particle Morphology Characterization

Figure 2 shows scanning electron micrographs of the two types of pigment particles investigated. Both pigments were supplied as free-flowing powders; however, significant differences in their particle morphology and size distribution are evident. As summarized in Table 2, pigment M1 has considerably larger particles, with sizes ranging from 20 to 200 μm , whereas pigment C1 consists of much finer particles, with sizes between 5 and 50 μm .

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of pigment particle M1 (**left**) and pigment particle C1 at 500x magnification (**right**).

Effect pigments based on borosilicate flakes (M series pigments) have neutral color, high luster, and attractive sparkling properties. Such pigments consist mostly of calcium–aluminum borosilicate platelets coated with metal oxide layers, e.g., SiO₂, TiO₂ or Fe₂O₃. Synthetically manufactured high quality flakes are absolutely planar and show a very smooth surface. They are characterized by a relatively uniform thickness of each single particle and, therefore, typically show a homogeneous color of each platelet. Special effect pigments, based on borosilicate flakes, possess in most cases particle diameters below 200 μm and a thickness below 2 μm. Depending on the flake geometry and the coating, the pigments provide a unique and striking multicolored sparkle effect in application systems. This appearance, which is particularly visible in systems pigmented with silver-white types, is called the multicolor effect.

Effect pigments based on silica flakes (C series pigments) can be used instead of natural or synthetic mica as a substrate for special effect pigments. The flakes are produced by a web coating process. SiO₂ flakes offer several advantages over the use of mica. Their thickness can be controlled during preparation so that at the end a pigment with a true optical three-layer system is obtained, the interference color of those systems being stronger than that for the conventional mica pigments, where the effect of the mica is levelled by a broad thickness distribution [15,28].

3.2. Colorimetric Characterization of Printed Effect Pigments

Figure 3 shows the color variability through *a*b** color coordinates of the printed pigments (M1–M3 and C1–C3) measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (−15°, 15°, 25°, 45°, 75°, and 110°) under different illuminants D50, A2, and F2.

The color effects of special effect pigments depend on the viewing angle. The platelets of the pigments split white light into two complementary colors depending on their thickness. The reflected (interference) color dominates under regular (maximum) reflection. This applies when the object is observed at the angle of regular reflection. The transmitted color dominates at other viewing angles under diffuse viewing conditions when there is a nonabsorbing (white) or reflecting background. Variation of the viewing angle leads at one point to a sharp peak reflectance (luster) and the color changes between two complementary colors [15]. The optical effects produced by effect pigments are closely linked to how these pigments interact with visible light, particularly through reflection, refraction, interference, and scattering [14].

The analysis of the pigments M1–M3 and C1–C3 (Figure 3) within the CIEL*a*b* color space reveals distinct variations in color variability and illuminant sensitivity. Among the M-series interference pigments, M1 shows the most significant color variability, particularly under the F2 illuminant. Its chromaticity coordinates shift from $a^* = 0.54$ and $b^* = -1.84$ at an aspecular angle of 110° to $a^* = 42.96$ and $b^* = -87.92$ as the angle reaches −15°. In comparison, the *a*b** values recorded under the D50 and A2 illuminants are slightly lower, indicating a relative decrease in saturation under these lighting conditions compared to the peak values observed under F2. In contrast, multicolor pigments (C-series) indicate distinct color-shifting behaviors and varying levels of sensitivity to light sources within the *a*b** chromatic coordinates. At the near-aspecular angle of −15°, C1 pigment achieves its highest value ($a^* = -40.23$, $b^* = 33.59$) at illuminant D50. Pigment C2 shows a color variability path that extends into the fourth quadrant, characterizing it as a magenta-purple effect pigment. Starting from near-neutral coordinates at far-aspecular angles (75° and 110°), the pigment moves toward increased saturation in the red-purple direction as

the angle decreases. For pigment 3, the color range extends into the first and second quadrants of the color coordinate system. The multicolor effect pigments (C-series pigments) exhibited more pronounced color variability than the interference pigments (M-series pigments) because of differences in chemical composition and multilayer structure. C-series pigments are engineered with multiple interference layers of precisely controlled thicknesses deposited on platelet-shaped substrates.

Figure 3. Color variability through the a^* , b^* color coordinates of the printed pigments M1–M3 and C1–C3, measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (-15° to 110°) under different illuminants D50, A2, and F2.

Table 3 shows the lightness difference (ΔL^*) of the printed pigments (M1–M3 and C1–C3) measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (-15° , 15° , 25° , 45° , 75° , and 110°). The lightness differences for illuminants A2 and F2 were calculated using the D50 illuminant as the reference.

Table 3. Lightness differences (ΔL^*) of the printed pigments.

Pigment	Illumination	Measurement Geometry					
		45as-15°	45as15°	45as25°	45as45°	45as75°	45as110°
M1	A2	1.97	2.36	1.15	0.21	0.02	0.02
	F2	4.87	3.54	1.57	0.26	0.05	0.04
M2	A2	2.78	1.83	0.84	0.24	0.04	0.04
	F2	0.99	0.58	0.08	0.09	0.02	0.04
M3	A2	-2.38	-1.30	-0.47	-0.14	-0.12	-0.10
	F2	-0.24	0.59	0.24	0.02	-0.03	-0.03
C1	A2	1.85	-0.74	-0.75	-0.28	0.07	0.22
	F2	-0.62	-1.96	-1.38	-0.43	-0.03	0.10
C2	A2	-4.00	-1.69	-0.36	0.40	0.46	0.43
	F2	-0.32	3.56	2.04	0.36	-0.07	-0.76
C3	A2	-4.31	0.05	0.33	0.17	0.11	-0.01
	F2	-0.87	3.75	1.70	0.21	0.06	-0.07

Lightness differences (ΔL^*) for both pigment series show a slight angular dependency, with peak variations occurring at near-specular angles. In the M series, pigment M1 exhibits its highest lightness difference at the aspecular angle of -15° , reaching 4.87 under F2 illuminant. On the other hand, pigment M3 shows a negative shift of -2.38 under the A2 illuminant at the same geometry. In the C series, pigment C3 displays the most negative value of -4.31 at -15° under the A2 illuminant. As viewing angles approach the 75° – 110° “flop” region, both series converge to high stability, with ΔL^* values frequently dropping below 0.10, confirming that dynamic lightness effects are concentrated near the specular highlight.

Table 4 shows the color differences (ΔE^*) of the printed pigments (M1–M3 and C1–C3) measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (-15° , 15° , 25° , 45° , 75° , and 110°). The color differences for illuminants A2 and F2 were calculated using the D50 illuminant as the reference.

Table 4. Color differences (ΔE^*) of the printed pigments.

Pigment	Illumination	Measurement Geometry					
		45as-15°	45as15°	45as25°	45as45°	45as75°	45as110°
M1	A2	15.88	12.33	5.68	1.19	0.35	0.29
	F2	14.93	11.49	5.68	1.16	0.38	0.29
M2	A2	7.44	5.81	2.86	0.75	0.14	0.09
	F2	11.49	8.82	4.60	1.05	0.17	0.19
M3	A2	12.79	11.14	4.14	0.66	0.28	0.26
	F2	10.05	7.22	3.12	0.90	0.43	0.32
C1	A2	7.54	6.07	5.97	3.87	1.78	0.90
	F2	11.75	5.68	3.88	1.88	1.19	1.02
C2	A2	12.62	3.42	1.70	1.41	1.45	1.41
	F2	17.47	7.03	3.84	2.79	2.71	1.79
C3	A2	6.43	5.74	5.34	3.01	0.97	0.35
	F2	15.66	6.73	3.69	1.39	0.62	0.41

Both series of pigments (interference and multicolor) exhibit a characteristic angular dependency of the CIE color difference (ΔE^*), with the greatest deviations at near-specular geometries, specifically at aspecular angles of -15° and 15° . As shown in Table 4, among the M series pigments, pigment M1 exhibits the highest color difference (ΔE^*) at -15° ,

reaching 15.88 under the A2 illuminant. Meanwhile, among the C series pigments, pigment C2 shows the highest color difference at the same aspecular angle, reaching 17.47 under the F2 illuminant. It was observed that ΔE^* values for all pigments consistently decrease as the measuring angle increases. The lowest ΔE^* was observed for pigment M2 under the A2 illuminant at 110° , where ΔE^* was only 0.09. The highest color differences observed at the 45as- 15° measurement geometry are due to the strong angular dependence of light reflection from the pigment particles. The goniochromism of the pigments becomes more pronounced, leading to larger shifts in perceived color and consequently higher color difference values. At far-aspecular angles (45as 45° –45as 110°), the intensity of reflected light decreases. Illumination conditions can significantly affect the appearance of iridescent surfaces. When light comes from a point source, such as the Sun on a clear day, highly specular iridescent surfaces appear especially brilliant. In contrast, under diffuse illumination, such as cloudy conditions, both specularity and iridescence can be greatly reduced [9].

Table 5 shows the chroma differences (ΔC^*) of the printed pigments (M1–M3 and C1–C3) measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (-15° , 15° , 25° , 45° , 75° , and 110°). The chroma differences for illuminants A2 and F2 were calculated using the D50 illuminant as the reference.

Table 5. Chroma differences (ΔC^*) of the printed pigments.

Pigment	Illumination	Measurement Geometry					
		45as- 15°	45as 15°	45as 25°	45as 45°	45as 75°	45as 110°
M1	A2	5.32	-0.21	-0.59	0.03	0.18	0.15
	F2	-14.09	-10.48	-0.59	-1.09	-0.36	-0.28
M2	A2	-0.72	2.31	1.47	0.36	0.07	-0.07
	F2	10.38	5.70	2.07	0.74	0.16	-0.04
M3	A2	12.56	10.31	3.87	0.62	-0.22	-0.23
	F2	2.30	-1.47	-0.75	-0.10	0.39	0.22
C1	A2	6.80	-3.06	4.83	3.36	0.80	-0.29
	F2	4.11	4.41	0.17	-0.62	-1.19	-0.70
C2	A2	7.44	1.90	-1.08	-0.70	-0.81	-0.95
	F2	14.36	1.93	1.53	0.08	-0.16	0.35
C3	A2	-4.19	5.73	6.62	2.42	0.92	0.24
	F2	4.01	-5.27	-3.22	-0.99	-0.15	-0.36

The analysis across pigments showed that saturation shifts depend strongly on the complex interplay between the aspecular angle and the specific illuminant. Within the M series pigments, pigment M1 demonstrates pronounced sensitivity to the illuminant source at the near-specular geometry; it showed a positive chroma shift of 5.32 under the A2 illuminant, but a noticeable chroma change of -14.09 under the F2 illuminant at the same angle. Pigment M2 also showed a high chroma difference under the F2 illuminant at -15° , with a value of 10.38. In the C series pigments, the most obvious deviation was observed for pigment C2 under the F2 illuminant at -15° , where the chroma difference reaches 14.36. Furthermore, pigment C3 exhibits a direct “flip” in saturation at the 15° angle, shifting from a negative value of -4.19 under the A2 illuminant to a positive value of 4.01 under the F2 illuminant. At a 110° angle, the ΔC^* values for the M series pigments are nearly negligible, with the M2 pigment reaching as low as -0.04 under F2, while the C series pigments also stabilize, with pigment C3 recording values between 0.24 and -0.70. Ultimately, these results demonstrate that accurate characterization of printed effect pigments requires analyzing not only the total color difference, but specifically how the

chroma difference responds to different measurement geometries to fully understand the material's visual performance.

Table 6 shows the hue differences (ΔH^*) of the printed pigments (M1–M3 and C1–C3) measured at a fixed illumination angle (45°) and varying aspecular angles (-15° , 15° , 25° , 45° , 75° , and 110°). The hue differences for illuminants A2 and F2 were calculated using the D50 illuminant as the reference.

Table 6. Hue differences (ΔH^*) of the printed pigments.

Pigment	Illumination	Measurement Geometry					
		45as-15°	45as15°	45as25°	45as45°	45as75°	45as110°
M1	A2	14.83	12.10	5.53	1.17	0.31	0.25
	F2	0.72	3.11	1.69	0.29	0.12	0.08
M2	A2	6.86	5.00	2.30	0.61	0.12	0.04
	F2	4.83	6.70	4.10	0.73	0.06	0.18
M3	A2	0.42	4.02	1.38	0.18	0.12	0.08
	F2	9.78	7.04	3.01	0.89	0.17	0.24
C1	A2	2.67	5.19	3.43	1.90	1.59	0.83
	F2	10.99	2.99	3.62	1.72	0.08	0.74
C2	A2	10.17	2.29	1.27	1.16	1.11	0.94
	F2	9.48	5.75	2.87	2.77	2.70	1.58
C3	A2	2.28	0.33	2.25	1.78	0.29	0.26
	F2	15.12	1.86	0.62	0.95	0.59	0.18

The analysis of the hue difference (ΔH^*) data across multiple measurement geometries and illuminants showed that, for both the M and C series pigments, hue shifts depend strongly on the aspecular viewing angle, with the most significant deviations usually occurring at near-specular geometries (-15° and 15°). In the M series pigments, pigment M1 shows strong hue sensitivity at an angle of -15° under the A2 illuminant, reaching a peak difference of 14.83, while its response under the F2 illuminant at the same angle is significantly lower at only 0.72. Conversely, as the viewing angle approaches the “flop” region (75° to 110°), the hue differences for the entire M-series stabilize considerably, with values consistently dropping below 0.31, indicating a highly uniform color appearance at far-aspecular angles. In the C series pigments, pigment C3 shows a sharp peak in hue difference of 15.12 under the F2 illuminant at 15° , highlighting pronounced color variability near the specular highlight. These results confirm that a multi-angle and multi-illuminant approach is essential for characterizing effect pigments, as the non-linear hue shifts documented here define their unique visual identity.

Table 7 shows the Pearson's correlation coefficient for all pigments analyzed ($N = 72$), based on the data in Tables 3–6. Pearson's correlation coefficient is defined as follows:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n ((x_i - \bar{x}) * (y_i - \bar{y}))}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} * \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (8)$$

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is a statistical measure that quantifies the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. The coefficient ranges from -1 to $+1$, where $+1$ indicates a perfect positive linear correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative linear correlation, and 0 indicates no linear relationship. Generally, absolute values of r greater than 0.7 are considered strong correlations, values between 0.4 and 0.7 indicate moderate correlations, and values below 0.4 represent weak correlations. The variables x_i and y_i relate to individual data points for variables X and Y ; \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the means (average) of variable X and variable Y ; and the Σ is the “sum of” all corresponding values [31]. In this study, Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to evaluate the relationship

between measurement geometry and illumination based on color differences (ΔE^*), lightness differences (ΔL^*), chroma differences (ΔC^*), and hue differences (ΔH^*).

Table 7. Pearson's correlation coefficient of the color, lightness, chroma and hue differences.

Pigment	Illumination	Pearson's Corr. Coefficient (r)			
		ΔE^*	ΔL^*	ΔC^*	ΔH^*
M1	A2	-0.8781	-0.8473	-0.5503	-0.8782
	F2	-0.8836	-0.8731	0.7815	0.5488
M2	A2	-0.8918	-0.8785	-0.1984	-0.8860
	F2	-0.8918	-0.7944	-0.8532	-0.8226
M3	A2	-0.8521	0.8263	-0.8691	-0.4327
	F2	-0.8712	-0.1487	-0.1801	-0.8738
C1	A2	-0.9825	-0.2623	-0.4668	-0.7030
	F2	-0.8606	0.6607	-0.7889	-0.8127
C2	A2	-0.7069	0.8260	-0.7362	-0.6995
	F2	-0.7911	-0.4523	-0.7063	-0.8405
C3	A2	-0.9662	0.6011	0.0223	-0.6580
	F2	-0.8402	0.6640	-0.0868	-0.6859

The results revealed predominantly strong negative correlations for ΔE^* across all pigments and illumination conditions ($r = -0.7069$ to -0.9825), indicating that color differences generally decreased as the measurement geometry shifted from near-specular to far-aspecular angles. Similar behavior was observed for ΔH^* , suggesting that hue differences were also most pronounced at smaller observation angles and gradually diminished with increasing angle. The ΔL^* and ΔC^* values showed more variable correlations, depending on pigment type and illumination. This variability reflects the complex interaction between the structure of the pigments, their goniochromatic properties, and the spectral characteristics of the illuminants. Strong positive or negative correlations observed for certain pigments indicate a systematic angular dependence of lightness and chroma, while weaker correlations suggest a less pronounced influence of measurement geometry on these parameters.

3.3. Flop Index Characterization of Printed Effect Pigments

The flop effect describes the phenomenon where the lightness of metallic effect prints depends very much on the viewing angle. It varies from extremely bright at or close to the gloss angle to rather dark at inclined angles. The flop behavior of metallic prints is determined in practice by using the brightness contrast of printed surfaces during observation under different viewing angles. The flop index (FI) indicates the lightness change at different scattering angles [15–29].

Factors affecting flop index are the shape and the size of pigment particles and the way they are laid down. The observational angles are grouped into three categories, "near-specular": 15° or 25° , "mid-specular" (or diffuse: 45°), and "far-specular": 75° or 110° , and correlate to the instrumental viewing angles [32]. Figure 4 shows the calculated flop index of pigments measured under different illuminations (D50, A2, and F2).

Figure 4. Flop index of pigments M1–M3 (left) and C1–C3 (right).

The flop index (FI) is a key metric for assessing the angular lightness variation of effect pigments, with higher values indicating a more pronounced “color variability” or “flop” effect. In this study, the M series pigments are characterized by larger flakes, ranging from 20 to 200 μm , while the C series pigments consist of much smaller particles, between 5 and 50 μm . In the M series pigments, pigment M1 showed the highest flop index at all three illuminants (D50, 2, and F2), with similar values of approximately $\text{FI} = 27$. In contrast, pigment M3 showed the lowest FI values, ranging from approximately 14.7 to 15.8. Despite their smaller particle size, C series pigments exhibit the most significant flop index in the entire set. Pigment C1 maintains a remarkably consistent FI between 32.3 and 32.5 across all three illuminations. In contrast, pigments C2 and C3 show much lower FI under all three illuminations compared to pigment C1.

To evaluate the influence of illuminant type on the flop index (FI), Pearson’s correlation coefficients (r) were calculated for all investigated pigments as shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Pearson’s correlation coefficients of the flop index.

Pigment	Pearson’s Corr. Coefficient (r)
M1	0.9997
M2	0.7810
M3	-0.1332
C1	0.4748
C2	-0.8389
C3	-0.2495

The results revealed substantial differences among the pigments. Pigment M1 exhibited an almost perfect positive correlation ($r = 0.9997$), indicating that its flop index remained highly consistent across the tested illuminants (D50, A2, and F2). Pigment M2 also showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.7810$), suggesting a relatively stable angular color effect under varying illumination conditions. In contrast, pigment M3 demonstrated a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.1332$), indicating a slight decrease in the flop index with changes in illuminant and a higher sensitivity to illumination conditions.

Among the multicolor pigments, C1 exhibited a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.4748$), suggesting a limited dependence of the flop Index on the illuminant. Conversely, C2 showed a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.8389$), indicating that changes in illumination significantly affected its angular color appearance. Pigment C3 also displayed a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.2495$), reflecting a less pronounced but still noticeable sensitivity to illumination changes.

4. Conclusions

This study examined the goniochromatic behavior and optical properties of printed interference and multicolor effect pigments under different illumination conditions and measurement geometries. The results confirmed that both the illumination source and viewing geometry strongly influence the visual appearance, color variability, lightness, chroma, hue, and flop effect of printed effect pigments.

Differences between the D50, A2, and F2 illuminants produced noticeable variations in color variability. As explained in this study, the D50 illuminant was chosen as the reference illuminant, based on which the lightness differences, color differences, chroma differences, and hue differences for the A2 and F2 illuminants were calculated. This study showed that A2 and F2 illuminations have a negligible effect on the lightness difference for all examined pigments, while they have a noticeable influence on the color, chroma, and hue differences, particularly at near-specular angles of -15° and 15° . At far-aspecular angles (75° and 110°), the differences become negligible for all pigments investigated. These findings confirm that goniochromatic pigments exhibit highly non-linear optical behavior, which depends strongly on both illumination and observation conditions.

Flop index analysis revealed clear differences between the two pigment groups. Although the M-series pigments contained larger borosilicate flakes, the C-series pigments exhibited the highest flop effect overall, especially pigment C1, which maintained consistently high FI values under all illuminants. The results indicate that both particle size distribution and pigment composition strongly contribute to angular lightness variation and visual brilliance.

The findings of this study improve our understanding of the relationship between pigment structure, illumination conditions, and viewing geometry, and may support the optimization of goniochromatic materials for applications in printing, coatings, packaging, and decorative surfaces.

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